

Cartan-Thullen theorem for \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic convexity and a related problem

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Abstract:

Cartan-Thullen theorem is a basic one in the theory of analytic functions of several complex variables. It states that for any open set U of \mathbb{C}^k , the following conditions are equivalent: (a) U is a domain of existence, (b) U is a domain of holomorphy and (c) U is holomorphically convex. On the other hand, when $f (= (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n))$ is a \mathbb{C}^n -valued function on an open set U of $\mathbb{C}^{k_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{k_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{k_n}$, f is said to be \mathbb{C}^n -analytic, if f is complex analytic and for any i and j , $i \neq j$ implies $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z_j} = 0$, where $(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in \mathbb{C}^{k_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{k_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{k_n}$ holds. We note that a \mathbb{C}^n -analytic mapping and a \mathbb{C}^n -analytic manifold can also be easily defined.

In this paper, we show an analogue of Cartan-Thullen theorem for \mathbb{C}^n -analytic functions. For $n = 1$, it gives Cartan-Thullen theorem itself. Our proof is almost the same as Cartan-Thullen theorem. Thus, our generalization seems to be natural. On the other hand, our result is partial, because we do not answer the following question. That is, does a connected open \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex set U exist such that U is not the direct product of any holomorphically convex sets U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n-1} and U_n ? As a corollary of our generalization, we give the following very partial result. If an open \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex set U is convex, then U is the direct product of some holomorphically convex sets.

Also, f is said to be \mathbb{C}^n -triangular, if f is complex analytic and for any i and j , $i < j$ implies $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z_j} = 0$. Kasuya suggested that a \mathbb{C}^n -analytic manifold and a \mathbb{C}^n -triangular manifold might, for example, be related to a holomorphic web and a holomorphic foliation.

Keywords:

Stein space, pseudoconvex manifold.

1 Introduction

First, we generalize the notion of a holomorphic function.

Definition 1 (Structure sheaf) :

Let $k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{n-1}, k_n, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_{n-1}$ and l_n be natural numbers. Let U be an open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. Let $f (= (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n))$ be a map from U to $\mathbb{C}^{k_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{k_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{k_n}$. Then, f is said to be \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic (\mathbb{C}^n -analytic), if f is holomorphic and for any $a \in U$ and any $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $i \neq j$ implies $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z_j}(a) = 0$, where $(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$ holds.

Let $O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ denote the set of all \mathbb{C}^n -valued \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic functions on U . Then, $\{O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)\}_U$ is called the sheaf of germs of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic functions.

Example 2 :

(1) Let

$$\pi_j(U) := \{z_j \in \mathbb{C}^{l_j} \mid \exists z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{j-1}, z_{j+1}, z_{j+2}, \dots, z_n : (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in U\}.$$

Let f_j be a holomorphic function on $\pi_j(U)$. Then, (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) is a \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic function on U .

(2) Let ε be a small positive number. Let

$$U := \cup_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}} (\{z_1 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_1 - e^{\sqrt{-1}\theta}| < \varepsilon\} \times \{z_2 \in \mathbb{C} \mid |z_2 - \theta| < \varepsilon\}).$$

Then, $(\log z_1, 0)$ is a \mathbb{C}^2 -holomorphic function on U . However, $\log z_1$ is a multivalued function on $\pi_1(U)$.

Remark 3 :

(1) The composition of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic mappings is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic. So, a \mathbb{C}^n -analytic manifold can be easily defined with its structure sheaf.

(2) For $n = 1$, $\{O_l(U)\}_U$ is the sheaf of germs of holomorphic functions.

(3) (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic, if and only if $(f_1, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 0)$, $(0, f_2, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 0)$, \dots , $(0, 0, 0, \dots, 0, f_{n-1}, 0)$ and $(0, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, f_n)$ are \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic. Also, $(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n), (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ implies $(f_1 g_1, f_2 g_2, \dots, f_n g_n) \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$. Further, if a sequence $\{f_m\}_{m=1}^\infty$ in $O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ uniformly converges to $g \in (O_{l_1 + l_2 + \dots + l_n}(U))^n$ on compact sets, then $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ holds. So, $O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ is the direct product of closed \mathbb{C} -subalgebras of the usual one $O_{l_1 + l_2 + \dots + l_n}(U)$.

(4) When A is a commutative Banach algebra, Lorch ([2]) gave a definition that an A -valued function on an open set of A is A -holomorphic. With the norm $\max_{j=1, 2, \dots, n} |z_j|$, \mathbb{C}^n is a locally compact one. We did a little study on A -analytic manifolds ([3, 4]). —

Since the structure sheaf $\{O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)\}_U$ was defined, we define \mathbb{C}^n -existence, \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy and \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic convexity. Just in case, we state uniqueness theorem.

Proposition 4 :

Let U be a connected open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. Let $f, g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$. Let $a \in U$. If for any multi-index α , $\frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} f}{\partial z^\alpha}(a) = \frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} g}{\partial z^\alpha}(a)$ holds, then $f = g$ holds.

Proof : It is an easy corollary of the usual uniqueness theorem. ■

Definition 5 (Existence, Holomorphy) :

Let U be an open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$.

(1) U is said to be a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence, if the following holds. There exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any open sets V and W of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$, if V is connected and $\emptyset \neq V \setminus U$ and $\emptyset \neq W \subset U \cap V$ hold, then for any $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(V)$, $f|_W \neq g|_W$ holds.

(2) U is said to be a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy, if the following holds. For any open sets V and W of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$, if V is connected and $\emptyset \neq V \setminus U$ and $\emptyset \neq W \subset U \cap V$ hold, then there exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(V)$, $f|_W \neq g|_W$ holds.

Lemma 6 :

\mathbb{C}^n -existence implies \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy.

Proof : It is obvious. ■

Definition 7 (Holomorphic convexity) :

Let $|\{w_k\}_{k=1}^m|$ denote $\max_{k=1, 2, \dots, m} |w_k|$ for $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m \in \mathbb{C}$. Let U be an open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$.

(1) Let K be a compact subset of U . Let

$$\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U := \{z \in U \mid \forall f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U) : |f(z)| \leq \sup_{w \in K} |f(w)|\}.$$

Then, $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is called the \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex hull of K .

(2) U is said to be \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex, if for any compact subset K of U , $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is compact. —

The following is the main result. We note that for $n = 1$, it is Cartan-Thullen theorem ([1]) itself.

Theorem 8 :

Let U be an open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. Then, the following conditions are equivalent: (a) U is a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence, (b) U is a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy and (c) U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex.

Remark 9 :

Let $U_j (\neq \emptyset)$ be a connected open set of \mathbb{C}^{l_j} ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$). Let $U := U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_n$.

(1) Let K_j be a compact subset of U_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$). Then,

$$(K_1 \times \widehat{K_2} \times \dots \times K_n)_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U = \widehat{K_{1l_1}}^{U_1} \times \widehat{K_{2l_2}}^{U_2} \times \dots \times \widehat{K_{nl_n}}^{U_n}$$

holds.

(2) U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex, if and only if U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n-1} and U_n are holomorphically convex.

Proof : (1) $U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_{j-1} \times U_{j+1} \times U_{j+2} \times \dots \times U_n$ is connected. Hence, if $(f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ holds, then for any $a_j \in U_j$, the function $(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{j-1}, z_{j+1}, z_{j+2}, \dots, z_n) \mapsto f_j(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{j-1}, a_j, z_{j+1}, z_{j+2}, \dots, z_n)$ is constant. So, $O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U) = O_{l_1}(U_1) \times O_{l_2}(U_2) \times \dots \times O_{l_n}(U_n)$ holds. For any $(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n) \in U$,

$$\forall f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U) : |f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)| \leq \sup_{w \in K_1 \times K_2 \times \dots \times K_n} |f(w)|$$

$$\iff$$

$$\forall (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) \in O_{l_1}(U_1) \times O_{l_2}(U_2) \times \dots \times O_{l_n}(U_n)$$

$$: \max_{i=1, 2, \dots, n} |f_i(z_i)| \leq \max_{i=1, 2, \dots, n} (\sup_{w_i \in K_i} |f_i(w_i)|)$$

$$\iff$$

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}, \forall f_i \in O_{l_i}(U_i) : |f_i(z_i)| \leq \sup_{w_i \in K_i} |f_i(w_i)|$$

holds.

(2) Suppose that U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. We show that U_j is holomorphically convex. Let K_j be a compact subset of U_j . There exists $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in U$. From (1),

$$\begin{aligned} & (\{a_1\} \times \{a_2\} \times \dots \times \{a_{j-1}\} \times \widehat{K_j} \times \{a_{j+1}\} \times \{a_{j+2}\} \times \dots \times \{a_n\})_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U \\ &= \widehat{\{a_1\}}_{l_1}^{U_1} \times \widehat{\{a_2\}}_{l_2}^{U_2} \times \dots \times \widehat{\{a_{j-1}\}}_{l_{j-1}}^{U_{j-1}} \times \widehat{K_{jl_j}}^{U_j} \times \widehat{\{a_{j+1}\}}_{l_{j+1}}^{U_{j+1}} \times \widehat{\{a_{j+2}\}}_{l_{j+2}}^{U_{j+2}} \times \dots \times \widehat{\{a_n\}}_{l_n}^{U_n} \end{aligned}$$

holds. Hence,

$$\pi_j((\{a_1\} \times \{a_2\} \times \dots \times \{a_{j-1}\} \times \widehat{K_j} \times \{a_{j+1}\} \times \{a_{j+2}\} \times \dots \times \{a_n\})_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U) = \widehat{K_{jl_j}}^{U_j}$$

holds. Because U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex, $\widehat{K}_{j l_j}^{U_j}$ is compact. U_j is holomorphically convex.

Suppose that U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n-1} and U_n are holomorphically convex. We show that U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. Let K be a compact subset of U . Then, there exists $\{K_j\}_{j=1}^n$ such that K_j is a compact subset of U_j and $K \subset K_1 \times K_2 \times \dots \times K_n$ holds. So, from (1),

$$\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U \subset \widehat{K}_{1 l_1}^{U_1} \times \widehat{K}_{2 l_2}^{U_2} \times \dots \times \widehat{K}_{n l_n}^{U_n} (\subset U)$$

holds. Because U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n-1} and U_n are holomorphically convex, $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is compact. U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. ■

Our generalization is considered natural. On the other hand, our result is partial, because we do not answer the following question.

Question :

Does a connected \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex open set U exist such that U is not the direct product of any holomorphically convex ones U_1, U_2, \dots, U_{n-1} and U_n ? —

Now, we can give the following very partial result.

Corollary 10 :

Let U be a convex open set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$.

(1) Let $f \in \mathcal{O}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$. Then, there exists $g \in \mathcal{O}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(\pi_1(U) \times \pi_2(U) \times \dots \times \pi_n(U))$ such that $f = g|_U$ holds.

(2) Suppose that U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. Then, $U = \pi_1(U) \times \pi_2(U) \times \dots \times \pi_n(U)$ holds.

Proof : (1) Let $f = (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n)$. For any $a_j \in \pi_j(U)$, $U \cap \pi_j^{-1}(\{a_j\})$ is convex, so, it is connected and the function

$$\begin{aligned} (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{j-1}, z_{j+1}, z_{j+2}, \dots, z_n) &\in U \cap \pi_j^{-1}(\{a_j\}) \\ \mapsto f_j(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{j-1}, a_j, z_{j+1}, z_{j+2}, \dots, z_n) &\in \mathbb{C} \end{aligned}$$

is constant. From this, it follows.

(2) From Theorem 8, U is a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence. Hence, from (1), it follows. ■

Comment :

A map f is said to be \mathbb{C}^n -triangular, if f is holomorphic and for any i and j , $i < j$ implies $\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial z_j} = 0$. Kasuya suggested that a \mathbb{C}^n -analytic manifold and a \mathbb{C}^n -triangular manifold might, for example, be related to a holomorphic web and a holomorphic foliation. —

2 Proof of main result

The proof of Theorem 8 is almost the same as Cartan-Thullen theorem. Perhaps, it seems to be also proved as a consequence of some general theory. However, for the sake of confirmation, we describe it. That is, we choose a proof that works in our case. In fact, it is extremely easy as we see below. When a reader believes that some proof which he knows works, he should skip the following proof.

Lemma 11 :

Let K be a compact subset of U . Then, $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is bounded.

Proof : Let $1 \leq k \leq l_j$. Then, $(0, 0, \dots, 0, z_{j,k}, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ holds. Here, $z_j = (z_{j,1}, z_{j,2}, \dots, z_{j,l_j})$ holds. Hence, $z \in \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ implies $|z_{j,k}| \leq \sup_{w \in K} |w_{j,k}| (< +\infty)$. ■

Lemma 12 :

Let K be a compact subset of U . Suppose that $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is not compact. Then, there exists

$$b \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U$$

such that

$$\inf_{a \in \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U} |a - b| = 0$$

holds.

Proof : From Lemma 11, $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is not a closed set of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. So, there exist a sequence $\{a_m\}_{m=1}^\infty$ in $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ and $b \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ such that $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} a_m = b$ holds. Because $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is a closed set of U , $b \notin U$ holds. ■

Lemma 13 :

Let K be a compact subset of U . Let

$$r := \inf_{z \in K, w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |z - w|.$$

Then, for any $a \in \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ and $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$, there exists $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(\{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z - a| < r\})$ such that for any multi-index α , $\frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} f}{\partial z^\alpha}(a) = \frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} g}{\partial z^\alpha}(a)$ holds.

Proof : Let $s \in (0, r)$. Then, from Cauchy inequality, there exists $c \in (0, +\infty)$ such that for any multi-index α ,

$$\left(\left| \frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} f}{\partial z^\alpha}(a) \right| \leq \right) \sup_{z \in K} \left| \frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} f}{\partial z^\alpha}(z) \right| \leq c \frac{\alpha!}{s^{|\alpha|}}$$

holds. Hence, $g : z \mapsto \sum_{\alpha} \frac{1}{\alpha!} \frac{\partial^{|\alpha|} f}{\partial z^\alpha}(a)(z - a)^\alpha \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(\{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z - a| < r\})$ holds. \blacksquare

Lemma 14 :

\mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy implies \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic convexity.

Proof : Suppose that U is not \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. Then, we show that U is not a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy. There exists a compact subset K of U such that $\widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is not compact. Let

$$r := \inf_{z \in K, w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |z - w|.$$

Then, from Lemma 12, there exist $a \in \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ and $b \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U$ such that

$$|a - b| < \frac{r}{2}$$

holds. Hence, from Lemma 13 and Proposition 4, U is not a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphy. \blacksquare

Lemma 15 :

Let $\{K_m\}_{m=0}^\infty$ be a sequence of compact subsets of U . Let $\{p_m\}_{m=1}^\infty$ be a sequence in U . Suppose that $U = \cup_{m=0}^\infty (K_m^\circ)$ holds and for any nonnegative integer m , $K_m \subset K_{m+1}$ and $p_{m+1} \in K_{m+1} \setminus \widehat{K}_{m, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ hold. Then, there exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \leq |f(p_m)|$ holds.

Proof : From $p_1 \notin \widehat{K}_{0, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$, there exists $g_1 \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_0} |g_1(w)| < |g_1(p_1)|$ holds. There exists $c_1 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_0} |c_1 g_1(w)| < 1 < |c_1 g_1(p_1)|$ holds. Then, there exists $k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_0} |(c_1 g_1(w))^{k_1}| \leq \frac{1}{2^0}$ and $2 + \sum_{j=1}^0 |(c_j g_j(p_1))^{k_j}| (= 2) \leq |(c_1 g_1(p_1))^{k_1}|$ hold. From $p_2 \notin \widehat{K}_{1, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$, there exists $g_2 \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_1} |g_2(w)| < |g_2(p_2)|$ holds. There exists $c_2 \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_1} |c_2 g_2(w)| < 1 < |c_2 g_2(p_2)|$ holds. Then, there exists $k_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sup_{w \in K_1} |(c_2 g_2(w))^{k_2}| \leq \frac{1}{2^1}$ and $3 + \sum_{j=1}^1 |(c_j g_j(p_2))^{k_j}| \leq |(c_2 g_2(p_2))^{k_2}|$ hold. Hereinafter, in the same manner, there exists a sequence $\{(g_m, c_m, k_m)\}_{m=1}^\infty$ such that for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $g_m \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$,

$c_m \in (0, +\infty)$, $k_m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sup_{w \in K_{m-1}} |(c_m g_m(w))^{k_m}| \leq \frac{1}{2^{m-1}}$ and $1 + m + \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} |(c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}| \leq |(c_m g_m(p_m))^{k_m}|$ hold.

For any $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sup_{w \in K_{m-1}} (\sum_{j=m}^{\infty} |(c_j g_j(w))^{k_j}|) \leq \sum_{j=m}^{\infty} (\sup_{w \in K_{j-1}} |(c_j g_j(w))^{k_j}|) \leq \sum_{j=m}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{j-1}} = \frac{1}{2^{m-2}}$ holds. So, $f := \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} ((c_m g_m)^{k_m}) \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ holds. For any $m \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + m + |(c_m g_m(p_m))^{k_m}| \\ = & 1 + m + \left| f(p_m) - \left(\left(\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} ((c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}) \right) + \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} ((c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}) \right) \right) \right| \\ \leq & 1 + m + |f(p_m)| + \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m-1} |(c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}| \right) + \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} |(c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}| \right) \\ \leq & \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} |(c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}| \right) + |f(p_m)| + |(c_m g_m(p_m))^{k_m}| \end{aligned}$$

and, so,

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 + m \\ \leq & \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} |(c_j g_j(p_m))^{k_j}| \right) + |f(p_m)| \\ \leq & \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} \left(\sup_{w \in K_{j-1}} |(c_j g_j(w))^{k_j}| \right) \right) + |f(p_m)| \\ \leq & \left(\sum_{j=m+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{j-1}} \right) + |f(p_m)| \\ = & \frac{1}{2^{m-1}} + |f(p_m)| \\ \leq & 1 + |f(p_m)| \end{aligned}$$

hold. ■

Lemma 16 :

Suppose that U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. Suppose $U \neq \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. Let $\{a_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence in U . For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, let

$$B_k := \{ z \in U \mid |a_k - z| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |a_k - w| \}.$$

Then, there exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)| = +\infty$$

holds.

Proof : Let

$$\begin{aligned} & ((q_1), (q_2, q_3), (q_4, q_5, q_6), (q_7, q_8, q_9, q_{10}), \dots) \\ & := ((a_1), (a_1, a_2), (a_1, a_2, a_3), (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4), \dots). \end{aligned}$$

Then, $\{q_m\}_{m=1}^\infty$ is a sequence in U and for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and $l \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $a_k = q_m$ and $l \leq m$ hold. Let $r_0 := 1, R_0 := 1$ and

$$\begin{aligned} & K_0 \\ & := (\cap_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid r_0 \leq |z - w|\}) \\ & \quad \cap \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z| \leq R_0\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, K_0 is a compact subset of U and, so, $\widehat{K}_{0, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ is a compact subset of U . Hence, there exists $p_1 \in U \setminus \widehat{K}_{0, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ such that $|q_1 - p_1| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |q_1 - w|$ and $\inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |p_1 - w| \leq \frac{1}{2}r_0$ hold. Let $r_1 := \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |p_1 - w|$, $R_1 := \max\{|p_1|, 2R_0\}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} & K_1 \\ & := (\cap_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid r_1 \leq |z - w|\}) \\ & \quad \cap \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z| \leq R_1\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $p_1 \in K_1 \setminus \widehat{K}_{0, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$, $0 < r_1 \leq \frac{1}{2}r_0 < +\infty$ and $0 < 2R_0 \leq R_1 < +\infty$ hold. So, K_1 and $\widehat{K}_{1, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ are compact subsets of U . Hence, there exists $p_2 \in U \setminus \widehat{K}_{1, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ such that $|q_2 - p_2| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |q_2 - w|$ and $\inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |p_2 - w| \leq \frac{1}{2}r_1$ hold. Let $r_2 := \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |p_2 - w|$, $R_2 := \max\{|p_2|, 2R_1\}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} & K_2 \\ & := (\cap_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid r_2 \leq |z - w|\}) \\ & \quad \cap \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z| \leq R_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, $p_2 \in K_2 \setminus \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$, $0 < r_2 \leq \frac{1}{2}r_1 < +\infty$ and $0 < 2R_1 \leq R_2 < +\infty$ hold. Hereinafter, in the same manner, there exist sequences $\{(r_m, R_m, K_m)\}_{m=0}^\infty$ and $\{p_m\}_{m=1}^\infty$ such that for any nonnegative integer m , $0 < r_{m+1} \leq \frac{1}{2}r_m < +\infty$, $0 < 2R_m \leq R_{m+1} < +\infty$,

$$K_m$$

$$= \left(\bigcap_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid r_m \leq |z - w|\} \right) \\ \cap \{z \in \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n} \mid |z| \leq R_m\},$$

$p_{m+1} \in K_{m+1} \setminus \widehat{K}_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}^U$ and

$$|q_{m+1} - p_{m+1}| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |q_{m+1} - w|$$

hold. Then, from Lemma 15, there exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \leq |f(p_m)|$ holds.

Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$. We show $\sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)| = +\infty$. Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $a_k = q_m$ and $l \leq m$ hold. Hence, $|a_k - p_m| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |a_k - w|$ and $l \leq |f(p_m)|$ hold. So, $l \leq \sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)|$ holds. Therefore, $\sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)| = +\infty$ holds. \blacksquare

Proof of Theorem 8 : Suppose that U is \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphically convex. We show that U is a domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence. When $U = \emptyset$ or $U = \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$ holds, it is obvious. Suppose $U \neq \emptyset$ and $U \neq \mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$. Then, there exists a sequence $\{a_k\}_{k=1}^\infty$ in U such that

$$U = \overline{\{a_k\}_{k=1}^\infty}$$

holds. For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, let

$$B_k := \{z \in U \mid |a_k - z| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |a_k - w|\}.$$

Then, from Lemma 16, there exists $f \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(U)$ such that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)| = +\infty$$

holds.

We show that U is the domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence of f . Suppose that U is not the domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence of f . Then, there exist open sets V and W

of $\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}$ and $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(V)$ such that V is connected and $\emptyset \neq V \setminus U, \emptyset \neq W \subset U \cap V$ and $f|_W = g|_W$ hold. Let

$$\tilde{W} := \{w \in U \cap V \mid \exists r \in (0, +\infty), \forall z \in U \cap V : [|z-w| < r \Rightarrow f(z) = g(z)]\}.$$

So, $\emptyset \neq \tilde{W} \subsetneq V$ holds and \tilde{W} is an open set of V . Because V is connected, \tilde{W} is not a closed set of V . Hence, there exists $b \in (V \cap \overline{\tilde{W}}) \setminus \tilde{W}$. We show $b \notin U$. Suppose $b \in U$. Then, $b \in (U \cap V) \cap \overline{\tilde{W}}$ holds. Hence, from Proposition 4, $b \in \tilde{W}$ holds. It is a contradiction. So, $b \notin U$ holds. Therefore,

$$b \in (V \cap \overline{\tilde{W}}) \setminus U$$

holds. Let $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$. Let $\delta := \min\{\varepsilon, \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus V} |b-w|\}$. Then, there exists $a \in \tilde{W}$ such that $|a-b| < \frac{\delta}{4}$ holds. Further, there exists $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $|a_k - a| < \frac{\delta}{4}$ and $a_k \in \tilde{W}$ hold. For any $z \in B_k$, $|a_k - z| < \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus U} |a_k - w| \leq |a_k - b| < \frac{\delta}{2}$ and, so, $|b-z| < \delta \leq \inf_{w \in (\mathbb{C}^{l_1} \times \mathbb{C}^{l_2} \times \cdots \times \mathbb{C}^{l_n}) \setminus V} |b-w|$ hold. Hence, $B_k \subset V$ holds. $B_k \subset U \cap V$ and $a_k \in B_k \cap \tilde{W}$ hold and B_k is connected. So, from Proposition 4, $B_k \subset \tilde{W}$ holds. Hence, because $z \in B_k$ implies $|b-z| < \delta \leq \varepsilon$,

$$(+\infty =) \sup_{z \in B_k} |f(z)| = \sup_{z \in B_k} |g(z)| \leq \sup_{z \in \{w \in V \mid |b-w| < \varepsilon\}} |g(z)|$$

holds. Therefore, for any $\varepsilon \in (0, +\infty)$, $\sup_{z \in \{w \in V \mid |b-w| < \varepsilon\}} |g(z)| = +\infty$ holds. However, since $b \in V$ and $g \in O_{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n}(V)$ hold, it is a contradiction. So, U is the domain of \mathbb{C}^n -existence of f .

Because \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic convexity implies \mathbb{C}^n -existence, from Lemmas 6 and 14, it follows. ■

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